

Argania spinosa
mitochondrial genome
707,441 bp

- complex I (NADH dehydrogenase)
- complex II (succinate dehydrogenase)
- complex III (ubichinol cytochrome c reductase)
- complex IV (cytochrome c oxidase)
- ATP synthase
- cytochrome c biogenesis
- RNA polymerase
- ribosomal proteins (SSU)
- ribosomal proteins (LSU)
- maturases
- other genes
- ORFs
- transfer RNAs
- ribosomal RNAs
- origin of replication
- polycistronic transcripts